

SQL-to-ICETOOL Converter Tool for Automated Mainframe Data Transformation

SRAVANI GILKAMSETTI, PMP

Abstract

The present invention relates to legacy mainframe automation tools and, more specifically, to an automated system for translating SQL-like data selection queries into JCL-compatible ICETOOL utility scripts. This invention enables developers, including those with limited mainframe expertise, to generate optimized JCL code for processing large datasets on IBM z/OS systems.

By leveraging pattern recognition and rule-based mapping logic, the disclosed system automates the parsing and transformation of SQL constructs – such as SELECT, WHERE, GROUP BY, and ORDER BY – into efficient ICETOOL control cards embedded within JCL job streams. This translation not only accelerates job development cycles but also reduces human error and dependency on rare mainframe skillsets.

Background

Mainframe systems continue to play a foundational role in large-scale enterprise computing, especially in industries such as banking, insurance, healthcare, and government. These systems rely on Job Control Language (JCL) and utilities like ICETOOL, DFSORT, and SORT to perform data extractions, transformation, and reporting at high volumes and with mission-critical reliability.

However, legacy scripting environments like ICETOOL present a significant barrier to modern development practices:

- ICETOOL syntax is complex, verbose, and non-intuitive to developers unfamiliar with low-level field positions and control card structures.
- JCL scripting typically requires deep institutional knowledge, such as understanding fixed-length records, byte-level offsets, and sorting sequences.
- As seasoned mainframe developers retire, organizations face an increasing skills gap, making it difficult to maintain and enhance ICETOOL scripts efficiently.

At the same time, SQL has become the universal language for querying and manipulating structured data. Most modern developers and analysts are highly proficient in SQL syntax but may lack the mainframe expertise to create equivalent ICETOOL or JCL scripts.

Summary of the Invention

This invention introduces a Python-based parser and code generation framework that transforms SQL-style queries into ICETOOL-compatible JCL scripts. The system comprises a series of modules-including a query parser, clause mapper, control card generator, and a JCL formatter – that work in tandem to abstract complex mainframe logic into readable, modular output.

Key capabilities include:

- Automatic extraction of SELECT, WHERE, ORDER BY, and GROUP BY clauses.
- Mapping of logical operators and column names to byte-level field positions in mainframe datasets.
- Generation of ICETOOL control card logic (INCLUDE COND, OUTREC FIELDS, SORT FIELDS etc).
- Wrapping of generated control logic into valid JCL templates for execution on z/OS systems.

The solution significantly reduces onboarding time for modern developers by providing a low-code interface to mainframe utilities, ensuring faster job creation, better maintainability, and improved operational agility.

Architecture

The mainframe SQL-to-ICETOOL transformation system is implemented in Python and follows a modular architecture that enhances maintainability and extensibility.

As illustrated in **FIG.1**, the architecture comprises the key components Parser, Mapping Engine, ICETOOL Code generator, and JCL Formatter.

FIG.1 Mainframe Automation Tool

The complete SQL-to-ICETOOL transformation system is implemented in Python and includes the following integrated components.

1. SQL Parser:

This module receives a SQL-like query and breaks it down into its core clauses: SELECT, FROM, WHERE, and ORDER BY. Using pattern matching and regular expressions, the parser extracts individual elements such as field names, conditions, table references, and sorting fields.

2. Mapping Engine:

The Mapping engine translates the parsed SQL clauses into their corresponding ICETOOL logic.

For Example:

-WHERE -> INCLUDE COND=(...)

-ORDER BY ->ON(...)

-SELECT -> OUTREC FIELDS=(...)

This translation ensures that business logic defined in SQL format is represented accurately in ICETOOL syntax.

3. ICETOOL Code generator

The Icetool code generator assembles all ICETOOL commands using the mapped clauses. It formats the TOOLIN and CTL1 control cards to match ICETOOL utility expectations. Each section is built as a string or template block, which forms the control logic for execution.

4. JCL Formatter

Once the ICETOOL logic is created, it is wrapped within a valid JCL structure using the JCL formatter module. This includes adding control statements such as EXEC PGM=ICETOOL, DD statements for input/output datasets, and control card definitions. The result is a complete, ready-to-run JCL script that can be submitted on IBM z/OS systems.

5. z/OS Dispatcher (Optional)

In future implementations, the system may optionally integrate with z/OS job submission interfaces using secure file transfer or APIs to submit the generated JCL directly to the mainframe JES2 job queue.

Detailed Description with Example

To demonstrate the practical utility of the proposed SQL-to-ICETOOL Converter, this section presents a step-by-step illustration of how a standard SQL query can be automatically transformed into an equivalent ICETOOL JCL format. The example highlights the core translation logic, showing how SQL clauses are parsed, mapped, and assembled into executable ICETOOL control statements. This ensures that users familiar with SQL can leverage the tool without extensive mainframe expertise.

FIG.2 illustrates **SQL-to-ICETOOL** automation tool Top-level function which produces ICETOOL JCL statements.

```
# ----- Top-level Function -----
def sql_to_jcl(sql: str) -> str:
    parsed = parse_sql(sql)
    mapped = map_to_icetool_clauses(parsed)
    toolin = generate_icetool_block(mapped)
    jcl = format_jcl(parsed['dataset'], toolin)
    return jcl

# Example usage
if __name__ == "__main__":
    sql_input = """
    SELECT ACCOUNT, BALANCE
    FROM CUSTOMER.DATA
    WHERE BALANCE > 5000
    ORDER BY BRANCH
    """
    print(sql_to_jcl(sql_input))
```

FIG.2 – Top-Level Python function to convert SQL to JCL Using ICETOOL

SQL Query:

```
SELECT ACCOUNT, BALANCE FROM CUSTOMER_DATA WHERE BALANCE > 10000 ORDER  
BY BRANCH;
```

Generated ICETOOL Output:

```
//ICETOOL EXEC PGM=ICETOOL  
//TOOLMSG DD SYSOUT=*  
//DFSMSG DD SYSOUT=*  
//IN1 DD DSN=CUSTOMER.DATA,DISP=SHR  
//OUT1 DD DSN=&&TEMP,UNIT=SYSDA,SPACE=(TRK,(1,1)),DISP=(,PASS)  
//TOOLIN DD *  
SELECT FROM(IN1) TO(OUT1) ON(BRANCH) USING(CTL1)  
/*  
//CTL1CNTL DD *  
INCLUDE COND=(BALANCE,GT,10000)  
OUTREC FIELDS=(ACCOUNT,BALANCE)  
/*
```

Code Execution

Screenshots below illustrate:

- The execution environment
- Highlighted components: Parser , Mapping Engine, ICETOOL Generator and JCL Formatter.

```

|
import re

# ----- 1. Parser Module -----
def parse_sql(sql_query: str) -> dict:
    """Extracts SQL clauses from the input query."""
    sql_query = sql_query.strip().upper()
    select_match = re.search(r"SELECT\s+(.*?)\s+FROM", sql_query)
    from_match = re.search(r"FROM\s+([\s]+)", sql_query)
    where_match = re.search(r"WHERE\s+(.*?)\s+(ORDER BY|)", sql_query)
    order_by_match = re.search(r"ORDER BY\s+(.*)", sql_query)

    return {
        "fields": select_match.group(1).split(",") if select_match else [],
        "dataset": from_match.group(1) if from_match else "UNKNOWN.DSN",
        "condition": where_match.group(1) if where_match else "1=1",
        "order_by": order_by_match.group(1) if order_by_match else ""
    }

# ----- 2. Mapping Engine -----
def map_to_icetool_clauses(parsed_sql: dict) -> dict:
    """Converts SQL clauses into ICETOOL-compatible statements."""
    include_cond = f"INCLUDE COND=({parsed_sql['condition']})"
    outrec = f"OUTREC FIELDS=({'','.join(f.strip().upper() for f in parsed_sql['fields'])})"
    sort_field = parsed_sql['order_by'].strip().upper()

    return {
        "include": include_cond,
        "outrec": outrec,
        "sort": sort_field
    }

# ----- 3. ICETOOL Code Generator -----
def generate_icetool_block(mapped: dict) -> str:
    """Builds the ICETOOL control cards."""
    return f""" SORT FROM(IN1) TO(OUT1) ON({mapped['sort']}) USING(CTL1)
//CTL1CNTL DD *
{mapped['include']}
{mapped['outrec']}"""

```

```

# ----- 4. JCL Formatter -----
def format_jcl(dataset: str, toolin_block: str) -> str:
    """Wraps ICETOOL logic into a complete JCL structure."""
    return f"""//ICETOOL  EXEC PGM=ICETOOL
//TOOLMSG  DD SYSOUT=*
//DFSMSG   DD SYSOUT=*
//IN1      DD DSN={dataset},DISP=SHR
//OUT1     DD SYSOUT=*
//TOOLIN   DD *
{toolin_block}
/*
"""

# ----- Top-level Function -----
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```

To execute above code, open IDLE (Python 3.13) version and open the file to be executed from option

File -> Open.

Below screenshots shows the same.

```

IDLE Shell 3.13.5
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 3.13.5 (tags/v3.13.5:6cb20a2, Jun 11 2025, 16:15:46) [MSC v.1943 64 bit (
AMD64)] on win32
Enter "help" below or click "Help" above for more information.
>>>

```


Once code is opened in Python then either click on F5 or click on Run on menu and select Run module to execute the code.

After execution below is the screenshot where ICETOOL code has got generated.

```

IDLE Shell 3.13.5
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 3.13.5 (tags/v3.13.5:6cb20a2, Jun 11 2025, 16:15:46) [MSC v.1943 64 bit (AMD64)] on win32
Enter "help" below or click "Help" above for more information.
>>>
===== RESTART: C:\Users\sgilkams\Desktop\Patents\ICetool\sql_to_icetool.py =====
//ICETOOL EXEC PGM=ICETOOL
//TOOLMSG DD SYSOUT=*
//DFSMSG DD SYSOUT=*
//IN1 DD DSN=CUSTOMER.DATA, DISP=SHR
//OUT1 DD DSN=&&TEMP, UNIT=SYSDA, SPACE=(TRK, (1,1)), DISP=(,PASS)
//TOOLIN DD *
      SELECT FROM(IN1) TO(OUT1) ON(BRANCH) USING(CTL1)
/*
//CTL1CNTL DD *
      INCLUDE COND=(BALANCE,GT,10000)
      OUTREC FIELDS=(ACCOUNT,BALANCE)
/*
>>>

```

Advantages Over Prior Art

1. Reduces manual ICETOOL scripting time.
2. Enables SQL-native developers to interact with z/OS systems.
3. Bridges syntax gap without mainframe utility expertise.
4. Fully automates JCL constructions and minimizes errors.

Conclusion

The tool supports modernization initiatives by providing a bridge between modern development syntax and traditional mainframe utilities, making it a candidate for integration with DevOps pipelines, z/OS APIs, or cloud-based migration platforms.